

Social media exposure, cyberbullying, and adolescent mental health: Examining the role of parental awareness and parent–teen communication

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Abstract:

The increasing use of social media among adolescents has raised growing concerns regarding its potential impact on psychological well-being. This study examines the relationship between social media exposure, cyberbullying experiences, parental awareness, parent–teen communication, and adolescent mental health outcomes. A quantitative cross-sectional survey was conducted among 110 parents of adolescents aged 13–19 years. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and multiple regression techniques. The findings indicate that higher levels of social media exposure are significantly associated with increased psychological distress and greater exposure to cyberbullying among adolescents. The results also suggest that parental awareness of online risks positively influences communication between parents and teenagers. Furthermore, effective parent–teen communication was found to reduce perceived mental health concerns. The study highlights the importance of understanding adolescents' digital behavior while emphasizing the supportive role families can play in mitigating potential psychological risks associated with excessive social media use.

Keywords:

Adolescent Mental Health, Social Media Exposure, Cyberbullying, Parental Awareness, Parent– Teen Communication, Digital Behavior.
